

WAYS TO INCREASE EMPLOYMENT LEVEL IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

During the years of independence, much attention was paid to the issues of improving the standard of living of the population, providing decent jobs, and training personnel. At the same time, significant progress has been achieved as a result of effective economic reforms and a number of positive changes in areas related to intellectual potential. Due to the special attention paid to youth in the labor market, the share of employed people in relation to the total population is high.

Systematic work was begun to help them find a worthy place in society and support them in their work, showing initiative. Young people who take advantage of the opportunities created effectively demonstrate their abilities in all areas. Consequently, the task of meeting the need for independently thinking young personnel who deeply feel responsibility for the fate of the country is becoming increasingly urgent. It is advisable to use data from the State Statistics Committee and the results of studying employment issues of the Ministry of Labor for an objective assessment of the situation on the labor market, determining the size of the working-age population in accordance with international standards, and formulating a procedure for developing a balance of labor resources.[1] According to the balance of labor resources, in 2015 the total labor resources of the republic amounted to 18.3 million people, of which 99.4 percent are the working population, the rest are working teenagers and pensioners. In addition, it should be noted that 75.3 percent of the labor force or 13.8 million people are classified as the economically active population, of which 13.1 million people are classified as the employed population. It can be seen that the employment rate of the economically active population is 94.8 percent.[2] The remaining 4.5 million people in the labor force make up the economically inactive population, which makes up 24.7 percent of the total labor force. As mentioned above, by the end of 2015, the employment rate was 94.8 percent in relation to the economically active population and 71.4 percent in relation to the labor force.[3] Thanks to the effective functioning of the conditions and support mechanisms created for the development of small businesses in the country, the business abilities of the population are expanding and the entrepreneurial initiative of young people is increasing. These aspects, in turn, pave the way for the timely promotion of promising proposals and initiatives. As a result, a large part of the employed population works in the small business sector, and the sector's share of GDP increases. The fact that a wide path is open for the

development of KBHT has become an important factor in increasing employment and incomes of the population, one of the means of ensuring the stability of society and the consistent development of society. economics.[4]

This creates a solid basis for ensuring macroeconomic stability, economic development, and consistent growth in the level and quality of life of the population. Increasing income, in turn, qualitatively changes the financial situation of families. This is the most important priority, so to speak. At the same time, modernizing industrial enterprises and equipping them with modern technologies allows them to produce competitive products for the world market.[5] It should be noted that the development of industrial sectors, an increase in the volume of highly processed products, and the effective organization of the introduction of industry into the countryside expand the possibilities for the proportional distribution of productive forces in the regions. As a result of the work carried out in 2015 on employment in the structure of industries, the following picture emerged:

- in industry there are 1668.3 thousand people, the share in the total number of employees is 12.8%;
- share of agriculture and forestry – 27.7%;
- 1248.5 thousand people in construction, share of total employment 9.6%;
- 710.7 thousand people in transport and communications, the share in the total number of employees is 5.4 percent;
- 1481 thousand people in trade and catering;
- 3,053,000 people in the social sector, the share of total employment is 23.4 percent;
- KBXT's share of total employment was 78 percent.[6]

One of the reasons for temporary unemployment in our republic is the imbalance between labor supply and demand. That is, the majority of the unemployed population consists of unskilled workers and young people entering the labor market for the first time. On the contrary, the need for personnel with high qualifications and experience in sectors of the economy is increasing. If we analyze the distribution of employment of the economically active population by region, we can note some features.[7] Firstly, in the regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (65%), Jizzakh (63.4%), Namangan (67.5%), Kashkadarya (70.1%) and Surkhandarya (71.4%) labor resources, that is, the population with a low level of economic activity observed. Therefore, the share of the employed population in the total labor force in these regions is significantly lower compared to the all-Russian indicator.[8] These cases are associated with the complexity of the demographic process in these regions. Secondly, due to the uneven distribution of population and labor resources across regions, regions differ in the number of employees. In particular, as stated above, the regions with the highest share of the total employed population in the republic are Samarkand (11.1%), Fergana (10.9%), Kashkadarya (9.4%), Andijan (9.3 %), Tashkent (8.8%).) and Namangan (8.3%) regions and Tashkent city (8.4%), Syrdarya (2.7%), Navoi (it can be seen that it is equal to 3.2%), Jizzakh (3.4%) and Khorezm (5.3%). Thirdly, due to the uneven distribution of productive forces, employment in regional sectors has a different type, and employment in industry, construction, and transport is relatively high in Tashkent and the Tashkent, Fergana, Navoi, Samarkand and Bukhara regions.[9] In the field of agriculture, we can say about the high indicators of Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions. The above considerations indicate the need to increase the level of employment of the

economically active population in our country. To this end, by further improving the “Methodology for recording the unemployed population in need of employment by region”, developing the “Methodology for developing a reporting and perspective balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population”, it is necessary to introduce its use in practice in the regions of the republic.[10] Reporting and forecast balances of labor resources, employment and employment of the population are developed for the following purposes:

- determining the parameters for creating jobs to ensure employment of the population, primarily young people and people who have reached working age and are entering the labor market for the first time;
- assessment of the imbalance in the balance and structure of supply and demand in the labor market;
- determining the prospects of the labor market taking into account the strategy of socio-economic development of regions and sectors of the economy;
- determination of the scope of personnel training by educational institutions. This methodology should reflect the following:

Firstly, the model structure of labor resources, employment and employment balance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In order to eliminate possible difficulties in determining the future, this sample structure should reflect the name of the indicators, the algorithm for their calculation, the balance of the report, the estimate (for the current year) and the balance of the forecast (for the next year). year). Also in the lines of the model structure: the number of labor resources, that is, the number of economically active and economically inactive population by type; demand and supply of labor and the difference between them (balance “+” or “-”) by type; there should be a level of employment of the population by category.[1]

Secondly, a scheme for providing information to form a balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population. In this scheme, it is desirable to clearly indicate the content (name) of the information, the name of the ministry and department providing the information, the period for providing the information and the place of its provision. Thirdly, the organizational scheme for developing the balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population. The framework should include the name of the measures, stages and timing of implementation, as well as the organizations responsible for implementation, and should cover the following four areas:

- formation of an information base;
- development of balance sheet;
- development of a forecast balance;
- their application in practice.[2]

After the development and approval of the above standard structures and schemes, the competent ministries and departments of the republic, on the basis of these structures and schemes, will develop a reporting balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, in addition to the balance, it is necessary to develop a forecast balance for the next year of labor resources, employment and employment of the population for official ministries and departments:—population forecast indicators (demographic forecast);

- reporting balance of labor resources, employment and population

employment;—forecast parameters for the development of the socio-economic and economic network of the republic and regions;

➤ forecast indicators for the entry of graduates of educational institutions into the labor market;

➤ information is used to assess the need for personnel in the networks of government and economic management bodies.

In conclusion, we can say that by developing the above-mentioned methodology and its implementation, a comprehensive, high-quality and objective analysis of labor resources, employment and employment of the population, young people entering the labor market for the first time, a work platform has been created to improve the level. This makes it possible to annually use job creation and employment programs when developing projects and increase its effectiveness in practice.

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